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Virtualization of PCIe-Based Reconfigurable Multi-Accelerator Systems for the Edge-Cloud Continuum

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for high computational performance and energy efficiency in cloud infrastructures has led to the growing importance of the use of Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs). This allows the scaling of reconfigurable multi-accelerator systems that until now were implemented on FPGAs at the edge to deliver significant improvements in processing power and meet the growing demands of modern computing environments. By leveraging FPGAs and Peripheral Component Interconnect Express (PCIe) interconnects, the proposed solution aims to provide flexible, high-performance acceleration capabilities that can dynamically adapt to varying computational demands across cloud and edge environments.

In the continuum of edge-cloud computing, having access to computing resources as a unified entity is highly advantageous from the user's perspective. This requires transparently virtualizing the underlying hardware to move and scale user applications across different computing resources. This can be particularly challenging when using reconfigurable multi-accelerator systems due to their need to access the hardware underneath directly.

This Master Thesis presents an infrastructure to integrate these FPGA-based platforms in the edge-cloud continuum, allowing for the seamless deployment of user applications throughout its different layers. The infrastructure employs Kubernetes as a microservice-based solution to deliver and manage user applications across the continuum, and the ARTICo³ framework, extended to PCIe-based FPGAs in this work, to accelerate parallel sections of the target applications in hardware. As a result, the proposed infrastructure can distribute and accelerate any user application on any FPGA-based device in the continuum. This infrastructure could also potentially exploit multi-tenant computing, where computing resources are shared among users, maximizing resource utilization.

The benefits of the proposed solution, including virtualization, portability, and scalability, have been validated through an actual edge-cloud continuum implementation running the Mach-Suite benchmarks, indicating that the proposed infrastructure induces a worst-case overhead of 1.23% when compared against single node scenarios. In addition, two custom acceleration scenarios (i.e., the matrix multiplication and AES algorithms) have been evaluated to perform design space exploration for different nodes within the edge-cloud continuum, using elastic accelerator implementations to exploit higher degrees of inner-parallelism on platforms that are far from the edge and thus maximize performance and resource utilization.

Key words: Edge-Cloud Continuum, Virtualization, Reconfigurable Multi-accelerator Systems, FPGAs.

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List of Acronyms

AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AI	Artificial Intelligent
API	Application Programming Interface
AXI	Advanced eXtensible Interface
AXI4	Advanced eXtensible Interface 4
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CMS	Card Management Solution Subsystem
DMA	Direct Memory Access
DPR	Dynamic and Partial Reconfiguration
DFX	Dynamic Function eXchange
EEPROM	Electrically Erasable Programmable Read-Only Memory
EI	Edge Intelligence
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GbE	Gigabit Ethernet
vFPGA	virtual Field-Programmable Gate Array
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HDL	Hardware Description Language
HLS	High-Level Synthesis
H2C	Host-to-Card
C2H	Card-to-Host
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
KVM	Kernel Virtual Machine
LUT	Look-Up Table
MCAP	Media Configuration Access Port
ML	Machine Learning
MPSoC	Multiprocessor System-on-Chip
NoC	Network-on-Chip
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OCI	Open Container Initiative
OCT	Open Cloud Testbed
OpenCL	Open Computing Language
OS	Operating System
FaaS	FPGA-as-a-Service
FaaS	Function-as-a-Service
PaaS	Platform-as-a-service

IaaS	Infrastructure-as-a-service
SaaS	Software-as-a-service
RaaS	Resource-as-a-service
BAaaS	Background-Acceleration-as-a-service
RAaaS	Reconfigurable-Accelerators-as-a-service
RSaaS	Reconfigurable-Silicon-as-a-service
PCAP	Processor Configuration Access Port
PCIe	Peripheral Component Interconnect Express
PRR	Partial Reconfigurable Region
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
RC3E	Reconfigurable Common Cloud Computing Environment
RC2F	Reconfigurable Common Computing Frame
SIMT	Single Instruction, Multiple Threads
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SmartNIC	Smart Network Interface Card
SCF	Serverless Computing Fabric
VHDL	Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language
VM	Virtual Machine
VMM	Virtual Machine Manager
VF	Virtual Function
XRT	Xilinx Runtime
XDMA	Xilinx Direct Memory Access

1 Introduction

In a technology landscape where the demand for performance and efficiency is ever increasing, PCIe-based FPGA platforms have emerged as an innovative solution for accelerating applications in the cloud. In recent years, FPGAs have been mainly used on edge computing because they provide customized performance and energy efficiency. However, integrating FPGAs into cloud environments has been more complex and is now an emerging field that is gaining momentum. This chapter provides a reference context and a motivation for the project, followed by a detailed analysis of the technological framework supporting hardware acceleration implementation on FPGAs in cloud environments. In the end, the main goals to be achieved are presented.

1.1 Context and Motivation

The growing need to process large amounts of data and the advancement of applications such as Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligent (AI) have generated the need to find efficient and scalable ways to handle this type of information. Conventional methods that rely on the Central Processing Unit (CPU) and Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) have shown performance, scalability, and power consumption restrictions when facing these demanding tasks. For these reasons, the variety of hardware devices utilized in cloud computing is expanding. This has made it increasingly common for FPGAs to be deployed in data centers, opening up new opportunities for distributed application acceleration [1]. The data center infrastructures of large companies such as Alibaba, Amazon, Baidu, Huawei and Tencent already expose FPGAs to application developers [15].

Hence, FPGAs have emerged as a powerful and adaptable alternative to meet the challenges of cloud-based processing. The flexibility of FPGAs allows the hardware to be tuned to the particular needs of the applications, taking full advantage of parallelism and significantly decreasing latency. Likewise, FPGA resources in the cloud allow the effective scale of the infrastructure to adapt to changing workloads. Although the FPGAs are increasingly being incorporated in data centers, it does not imply that they will be maintained over time. They need new technologies to compete with the pair of CPU, GPU, and the latest AI-specific processors currently deployed and under development.

The integration at the board, system, and application levels should harness the strengths of the reconfiguration while mitigating its weaknesses. To provide hardware resources effectively, it is necessary to have sufficient middleware, appropriate hardware virtualization, and domain separation mechanisms. Efficient and flexible hardware resource provisioning can facilitate integration into existing cloud management infrastructures with minimal redesign.

In order to take advantage of the benefits provided by FPGA-based hardware acceleration infrastructures in cloud environments, it is necessary to design applications capable of exploiting the resources offered.

1.2 Technology Framework

The work developed in this project revolves around a technological scenario where different disciplines converge to increase the performance and flexibility of data processing and algorithm execution. This technological framework is based on the use of PCIe-based FPGAs, that offer powerful parallel processing and dynamic reconfiguration capabilities through the PCIe interface. In addition, ARTICo³, an optimized hardware acceleration infrastructure is integrated to exploit the full potential of these FPGAs. In parallel, the interaction between cloud and edge devices is explored through the edge-cloud continuum concept, enabling efficient workload distribution and agile response to the demands of the environment. Complementing these technologies, virtualization emerges as a fundamental pillar to create flexible and scalable environments independent of the physical infrastructure and thus facilitating the management and optimization of resources in the technological ecosystem that we address in this project. This section is organized into three key subsections: an overview of the edge-cloud continuum, a detailed discussion on integrating FPGA accelerators in the cloud, and an analysis of the virtualization of FPGA resources.

1.2.1 Edge-Cloud Continuum

The edge-cloud continuum refers to a seamless and integrated computing environment that spans from centralized cloud resources to distributed edge devices [16]. This continuum enables applications and services to dynamically utilize resources across this spectrum based on factors such as proximity, latency requirements, and workload characteristics [17]. This concept acknowledges that computing is not solely confined to the centralized cloud or edge devices. Instead, it encompasses a continuum of resources extending from the cloud to the edge of the network.

- At the cloud, fast computing resources, storage capabilities, and services accessible over the internet are available [18]. This centralized infrastructure is well-suited for handling large-scale processing, storage-intensive tasks, and services that do not require real-time responsiveness.
- On the edge side, there are devices located closer to where data is generated or consumed, such as Internet of Things (IoT) devices, gateways, or edge servers [18]. These devices offer advantages like reduced latency, improved data privacy, and the ability to process data locally, making them ideal for time-sensitive applications, real-time analytics, and scenarios where connectivity to the central cloud may be intermittent or constrained.

The continuum aspect comes into play when applications and workloads can seamlessly transition between cloud and edge resources based on changing needs. For example, data processing might start at the edge for quick initial insights and then move to the cloud for deeper analysis or long-term storage. This dynamic resource allocation optimizes performance, scalability, and cost-effectiveness across the entire computing continuum.

In short, the edge-cloud continuum represents the idea that computing is not simply centralized in the cloud or distributed across edge devices but encompasses a full spectrum of resources that can be efficiently integrated to meet the diverse needs of applications and users.

1.2.2 FPGA-based acceleration in the Cloud

FPGAs in the cloud represent a powerful convergence of hardware acceleration and cloud computing capabilities. Traditionally, FPGAs have been used in embedded systems and specialized edge applications due to their reconfigurable nature and parallel processing capabilities. However, with the advent of cloud computing, FPGAs are increasingly being integrated into cloud environments to enhance performance and energy efficiency for a wide range of applications [15].

One of the key benefits of using FPGAs in the cloud is their ability to accelerate specific workloads that require high computational throughput or specialized processing capabilities. This enables significant performance improvements and energy efficiency, making them ideal for tasks such as machine learning, data analytics, and real-time processing. FPGAs can be dynamically allocated and configured in the cloud to match the requirements of different tasks, providing a level of flexibility and performance that traditional CPUs or GPUs may struggle to achieve.

Moreover, FPGAs in the cloud enable developers to offload computationally intensive tasks from the main CPU or GPU instances, leading to improved overall system performance and reduced latency for critical operations. This is particularly advantageous for applications in areas such as data analytics, machine learning inference, financial modeling, and scientific simulations, where speed and efficiency are essential.

Cloud providers often offer FPGA instances as part of their Infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS), allowing developers and organizations to access FPGA resources on-demand without the need to invest in dedicated hardware. This approach democratizes FPGA usage and opens up new possibilities for accelerating and optimizing a wide range of applications in the cloud environment.

In summary, leveraging FPGAs in the cloud brings together the benefits of hardware acceleration, scalability, and flexibility, making it a compelling choice for optimizing performance and efficiency in modern cloud-based computing architectures.

ARTICo³

In this Master Thesis, the virtualization needs of reconfigurable systems in the edge-cloud continuum are addressed. To this end, a microservice-based solution [19] is proposed to deploy hardware-accelerated functions at all layers in a transparent manner. For this purpose, the ARTICo³ framework [12] has been selected as the underlying on-chip infrastructure. ARTICo³ enables the design and implementation of hardware-accelerated applications that exploit data- and task-level parallelism while providing low-level hardware virtualization capabilities (i.e., abstracts both acceleration implementation and FPGA reconfiguration mechanisms) and transparent template-based portability across different families and parts of the AMD Xilinx portfolio. As part of the work presented in this project, ARTICo³ has been extended from edge/fog platforms (i.e., host and acceleration fabric on the same device) to the cloud (i.e., host and acceleration fabric connected via PCIe links). ARTICo³ is then used at node level to accelerate those user applications in hardware. Subsection 3.1 explains the ARTICo³ baseline architecture in more detail.

1.2.3 Virtualization of FPGA resources

FPGA virtualization is the process of abstracting the physical resources of an FPGA to enable its flexible and efficient use in computing environments such as the cloud. This approach optimizes resource usage, avoids hardware underutilization, and allows dynamic allocation according to application needs, offering scalability and flexibility. In addition, it facilitates access to FPGA acceleration capabilities through standard interfaces and cloud services without requiring advanced hardware design knowledge.

Virtualization represents a significant factor in fostering the integration of FPGAs in cloud environments. The conversion of physical hardware resources into virtualized instances is based on the deployment of virtualization technologies, such as hypervisors and containers, which provide a layer of flexibility and resource management that complements FPGA-based acceleration in the cloud [6]. One of the key advantages of virtualization in the context of FPGAs is the ability to create isolated environments or Virtual Machines (VMs) that can be customized to support FPGA-accelerated workloads. This isolation ensures that different FPGA applications or users can coexist on the same physical infrastructure without interfering with each other, enhancing security and reliability.

Moreover, virtualization enables dynamic resource allocation and scaling based on demand. FPGAs can be allocated to specific VMs or containers as needed, allowing for efficient utilization of FPGA resources across different applications and users. This dynamic allocation also supports workload migration and load balancing, optimizing resource usage and overall system performance.

Additionally, virtualization facilitates the development and deployment of FPGA-accelerated solutions by providing standardized interfaces and management tools. Developers can create FPGA-accelerated virtual appliances or images that can be easily deployed and managed within virtualized environments, simplifying the deployment and maintenance process.

Furthermore, virtualization aligns well with cloud deployment models such as IaaS and Platform-as-a-service (PaaS), where users can access virtualized FPGA resources as part of their cloud service offered by third parties. This abstracted approach to FPGA utilization in the cloud promotes scalability, cost-effectiveness, and agility in deploying FPGA-accelerated solutions.

In conclusion, virtualization complements FPGA-based acceleration in the cloud by providing a flexible, scalable, and manageable environment for deploying and managing FPGA resources. It enhances resource utilization, security, and ease of deployment, making virtualized FPGA solutions an integral part of modern cloud computing architectures. The following paragraphs introduce the fundamental concepts of containerization and the Kubernetes container orchestrator, which have been used in this project.

- **Containerization**

Containerization is a virtualization technique consisting of packaging an application and its dependencies into an image that can be executed on any device or operating system. Applications within containers are isolated from the rest of the system, and all necessary components are self-contained. Containerization enforces portability, scalability, and fault tolerance, as images can be deployed in any system without interfering with each other, making containerization highly convenient for applications on the edge-cloud continuum. In some cases, isolation can limit communication with other applications and

systems or cause hardware reconfiguration and FPGA access problems. However, there are mechanisms such as storage volumes, network services, and device managers designed to overcome those limitations.

There are several widely used container runtimes, including Docker,¹ and CRI-O,² for creating, deploying, and managing containerized applications. However, most of these runtimes comply with the open container format standard named Open Container Initiative (OCI).³ This means that containers created with one runtime can be executed by others, further enhancing portability.

- **Kubernetes**

Kubernetes is an open-source platform widely adopted for container orchestration.⁴ Containerizing applications offers numerous benefits, as previously explained. However, managing a growing number of containers can become increasingly more complex. For example, multiple nodes (i.e., computing systems) may run several containers in an edge-cloud continuum environment. When using some specific container runtimes (e.g., Docker), each container must be deployed individually, along with any necessary additional resources, such as shared storage for data persistence or network services to enable inter- and extra-container communications. This process is tedious and prone to errors, which worsens as the system scales.

In contrast, Kubernetes provides a framework for running container-based distributed systems resiliently. Kubernetes enables transparent container deployment, storage, and network management while handling application scaling and failover. It can automatically deploy additional container instances and resources on the same or different nodes as needed. Additionally, Kubernetes enhances fault tolerance by seamlessly restarting or replacing failing containers or resources.

1.3 Goals of the Thesis

The main goals of this Master's Thesis are listed below:

- Study of the problems associated with the integration of PCIe-based platforms with multiple hardware accelerators in the cloud: Direct Memory Access (DMA) transfers and Dynamic and Partial Reconfiguration (DPR).
- Extending ARTICo³ framework for the cloud.
- Design a hardware virtualization infrastructure to integrate platforms with multiple hardware accelerators in the edge-cloud continuum, allowing for the seamless deployment of user applications throughout its different layers.
- Leveraging accelerator scalability to optimize area/performance throughout the continuum.
- Validate the designed architecture by testing in real scenarios.

¹<https://www.docker.com>

²<https://cri-o.io>

³<https://opencontainers.org>

⁴<https://kubernetes.io>

1.4 Structure of the Document

This section provides an outline for the remainder of the document and defines the areas on which each chapter focuses.

- **Section 2** is divided into two parts. The first part discusses different architectures developed by the community to integrate multiple hardware accelerators on cloud platforms. The second part of the chapter studies the various forms of FPGA virtualization and analyzes the different infrastructures proposed in the literature for implementation.
- **Section 3** describes the changes that have been necessary to adapt the ARTICo³ architecture for FPGA-based platforms.
- **Section 4** describes the proposed Kubernetes-based edge-cloud continuum infrastructure for reconfigurable multi-accelerator systems.
- **Section 5** validate the performance of the ARTICo³ framework by implementing elastic applications on different platforms within the edge-cloud continuum and compares the performance of the proposed architecture with the performance of the architecture without the virtualization layer.
- In **Section 6**, this Master Thesis discusses the conclusions and proposes future lines of development.
- **Section 7** shows the time planning of the project along with the budget.
- **Section 8** describes the social and professional impact through Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2 State of the Art

2.1 Introduction

As mentioned in the previous chapter, FPGAs are widely used for computationally intensive applications due to their efficient power consumption and intensive parallelism. They are, therefore, increasingly being used for cloud computing.

Cloud computing is a paradigm that is defined by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) as “a model for enabling convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, and applications) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction” [20]. Cloud computing provides three types of services using virtualization and dematerialization techniques. Each service offers users varying levels of control and management to suit their specific needs. The services are Software-as-a-service (SaaS), Platform-as-a-service (PaaS) and Infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS), but when an FPGA is incorporated it is known as FPGA-as-a-Service (FaaS) [21].

FaaS refers to an infrastructure of FPGA devices or software design tools available in the cloud. FaaS can also be divided into three service levels based on the three services cloud computing offers.

- **FPGA Software tools as a service:** This approach provides FPGA development and deployment capabilities through the cloud. By leveraging the cloud infrastructure, developers can access a suite of software tools for FPGA programming, simulation, and debugging without the need for local installations or high-performance hardware. The service typically includes High-Level Synthesis (HLS) tools, design entry tools, simulation environments, and configuration management systems, all accessible through a web-based interface or cloud API.
- **FPGA Platforms as a service:** This model allows application designers to access one or more FPGA platforms without purchasing them. The designer can develop and implement cloud applications on different FPGA platforms.
- **FPGA Resources as a service:** This model divides FPGA into multiple independent vFPGA regions. These regions can be provisioned to various application designers in a multi-tenant environment with virtual access to the physical FPGA.

Considering the different services above and the two most studied topics in the state of the art on FPGAs in the cloud, the section has been divided into two parts. The first one presents the different studies on cloud computing applications that have implemented FPGAs as standard hardware in data centers to accelerate remote applications. The second one shows studies focused on FPGA virtualization in the cloud to provide an abstraction of the FPGA hardware used.

2.2 FPGA platforms for cloud computing

Open Cloud Testbed (OCT)

The OCT [22] incorporates FPGAs in the cloud through three existing systems: The Massachusetts Green High-Performance Computing Center (MGHPCC),⁵ the Massachusetts Open Cloud (MOC),⁶ and CloudLab.⁷

Leeser et al. [1] present the OCT model as a combination of IaaS and PaaS where infrastructures include tools for development and are coupled with bare-metal deployment. This infrastructure gives users direct access to FPGAs in the cloud and allows them to experiment with the entire configuration, including the operating system.

The FPGAs are connected directly to the network, allowing direct connections between FPGAs and SmartNIC-based experiments. Figure 2.1 shows how the design flow is performed by the Xilinx Vitis tool with eight Xilinx Alveo U280s integrated into OCT with a predefined internal structure. As can be seen, this structure has a static region (shell) and a reconfigurable region (user partition), which are controlled from the host through the Xilinx Runtime (XRT) and the PCIe driver. The FPGAs are connected to the host processor via a PCIe and directly to the network via two independent 100Gbps connections. This allows direct communication between acpfpga via User Datagram Protocol (UDP) or Transmission Control Protocol (TCP).

Figure 2.1: Overview of the OCT infrastructure showing both the development platform and the target platform for the FPGAs [1].

⁵<https://www.mghpcc.org/>

⁶<https://massopen.cloud/>

⁷<https://www.cloudlab.us/>

RC2F

The RC2F [2] enables the integration of FPGAs in cloud environments, robust resource management, and user administration. It even supports the vFPGA concept, allowing the integration of user cores. The concept of vFPGAs involves abstracting physical FPGA resources into multiple virtual instances that can be dynamically allocated and managed across different users or applications within a cloud or virtualized environment. RC2F is integrated into the RC2F [23] environment, offering high-performance communication over PCIe. This framework is typically used in Resource-as-a-service (RaaS) and Background-Acceleration-as-a-service (BAaaS) models.

As can be seen in Figure 2.2, the **r2cf!** (**r2cf!**) framework includes a PCIe endpoint connected to user designs via a switch managed by a controller that oversees configuration and monitoring. This configuration supports up to four vFPGAs with independent user designs, enhancing security by restricting full bitstream access to research systems and promoting partial reconfiguration. An API facilitates communication between the host and FPGA, and the controller memory space is accessible from the host for various functions.

Figure 2.2: RC2F framework where the partial reconfiguration areas are integrated with the host system [2].

RACOS

The Reconfigurable ACcelerator OS (RACOS) [3] is a system designed to streamline the deployment and operation of reconfigurable hardware accelerators. It offers a user-friendly software interface for loading/unloading accelerators and managing data I/Os, supporting multiple partially reconfigurable regions on an FPGA. These regions can host single- or dual-threaded accelerators, effectively virtualizing the hardware resources. RACOS enables multiple applications to use accelerators and schedules them using four policies to optimize reconfiguration and execution.

The Figure 2.3 shows how the I/O hardware architecture is based on the Gen2 PCIe interface x4. The board is the bus master, and the DMAs are initiated in the Register File of the PCIe. The data are transferred to the Partial Reconfigurable Region (PRR) threads and the reconfiguration controller. The event dispatcher, informs the CPU regarding the system state.

Figure 2.3: Hardware architecture of RACOS [3].

Lallet et al.

The authors propose a framework [4] for managing hardware acceleration in such systems based on containerized applications. The FPGA device implements a partial reconfiguration engine in the processor, which handles hardware acceleration requests from host applications over the network. RIFFA[24] is used to transfer data between the host and the FPGA through the PCIe bus to minimize latency. The compute node consists of a server connected to an FPGA as shown in Figure 2.4. The server processes Virtual Function (VF) using containers, while a connected FPGA card via a PCIe interface handles the load function. The FPGA is divided into several acceleration slots to provide flexible and shared acceleration resources, enabling direct and independent access from the containers.

Figure 2.4: Overview of the Lallet et al. proposed framework [4].

2.3 FPGA Virtualization in the Cloud

In today’s cloud computing scenario, hardware virtualization plays a crucial role in creating flexible and scalable environments for deploying applications and services. This state-of-the-art section examines the development and trends of the leading hardware virtualization techniques in cloud environments, highlighting their applications, advantages, and challenges.

2.3.1 Virtualization with VMM/Hypervisor

In this section we will start by defining two very extended virtualization environments with VM, and once we have seen these two fundamental elements in system virtualization, we will proceed to analyze different works in the literature.

Xen is an open-source hypervisor that enables the creation, management, and execution of multiple VMs on a single physical hardware host.⁸ It provides an abstraction layer between the physical hardware and the operating systems, allowing multiple OS instances to run concurrently on the same hardware while sharing resources efficiently. Xen virtualization is widely used in cloud computing environments due to its robust architecture and strong performance isolation features. As a Type 1 or “bare-metal” hypervisor, it operates directly on the hardware, providing high performance and low overhead. Xen supports paravirtualization (PV) and hardware-assisted virtualization (HVM), enabling efficient interaction with the hypervisor for modified guest Operating Systems (OSs) and allowing unmodified guest OSs to run, respectively. The architecture of Xen includes a privileged management domain called Dom0, which controls the creation and management of user domains (DomU). Advanced resource management capabilities in Xen ensure efficient CPU scheduling, memory allocation, and I/O management, promoting fair resource distribution among VMs. Security is a significant strength of Xen, with solid isolation between VMs and features like disaggregated driver domains and secure boot. Additionally, Xen’s scalability supports many VMs on a single host, making it ideal for cloud environments.

Kernel Virtual Machine (KVM)⁹ is a full virtualization solution for Linux on x86 hardware containing virtualization extensions (Intel VT or AMD-V). It consists of a loadable kernel module, that provides the core virtualization infrastructure and a processor-specific module. Using KVM, one can run multiple virtual machines with unmodified Linux or Windows images. Each virtual machine has private virtualized hardware: a network card, disk, graphics adapter, etc., and does not use a dedicated hypervisor but makes the GNU/Linux kernel itself act as a hypervisor. The kernel can split the machine’s resources between several processes, so by introducing some modifications and making virtual machine processes, the kernel can do the job of a hypervisor. All these modifications are made in a kernel module, which will be loaded at boot time and used to create virtual machines.

Mandebi et al.

This work [5] defines FPGAs virtualization by introducing elasticity and multitenancy within the proposed hardware/software virtualization architecture. Hardware elasticity refers to the ability of a system to dynamically adjust its hardware resources to meet the changing demands of applications in real-time. It extends a KVM infrastructure with FPGA management capabilities, providing a software architecture to support FPGA allocation, release, and access in KVM

⁸<https://xenproject.org/>

⁹https://linux-kvm.org/page/Main_Page

clouds. It also leverages the Virtio [25] paradigm to establish efficient communication between virtual machines and FPGAs. In addition, it enables co-hosting of workloads on a single device, explores the use of a Network-on-Chip (NoC) topology to support FPGA multi-tenancy and hardware elasticity. It also facilitates spatial and temporal sharing of FPGAs logic among multiple cloud users with minimal performance degradation and resource overhead. Figure 2.5 shows the overall hardware/software virtualization architecture. It shows an overview of the components on FPGAs, as well as the software virtualization stack.

Figure 2.5: Mandebi et al. proposed architecture [5]

Knodel et al.

The work presented by [6] addresses a previously mentioned approach RC2F for deep reconfigurable hardware virtualization of FPGAs hardware in cloud-based environments. The proposed approach uses partial reconfiguration to abstract an FPGA into multiple independent vFPGAs. This enables users to request vFPGAs of various sizes to optimize resource utilization and energy efficiency throughout the entire cloud system. This virtualization creates a homogeneous partition over a heterogeneous FPGA by abstracting physical locations and static areas, facilitating flexibility and resource optimization. RC2F extension also supports virtualization with a security system for processing sensitive data.

Furthermore, the paper elucidates the role of the Reconfigurable Common Cloud Computing Environment (RC3E) in the proposed system. RC3E serves as the host, offering various service models (RSaaS, RAaaS, BAaaS), and managing the allocation of dynamic vFPGAs. Figure 2.6 shows an example deployment of FPGA virtualization based on KVM paravirtualization using this framework. This virtualization of FPGAs is limited to the interfaces and designs within the reconfigurable regions, constituting them as the non-privileged domain (DomU). The traditional design flow is used to generate the vFPGA, with predefined regions for dynamic partial reconfiguration and static interfaces. The infrastructure where the vFPGAs is hosted must be located in the static region corresponding to a privileged domain (Dom0) or hypervisor.

Figure 2.6: Proposed vFPGA architecture [6].

Suhaib et al.

The work presented in [7] proposes a framework that integrates reconfigurable accelerators into a standard server with virtualized resource management and communication between FPGA and the CPU. The proposed framework integrates an FPGA board into a standard data center server. The FPGA is divided into independent accelerator slots, and its reconfiguration and data transfer are managed through the PCIe interface. Acceleration functions are stored in a library on the host machine and can be loaded by the user. The communication interface implemented in the FPGA can handle multiple accelerators simultaneously, and an integrated arbiter guarantees fair bandwidth for each accelerator communicating with the server. Additionally, the accelerators are configured via PCIe to improve reconfiguration performance. They have also developed a software infrastructure to manage low-level communication and high-level virtualization through a controller and a hypervisor, respectively. Figure 2.7 shows the proposed architecture and its operational flow.

Figure 2.7: Proposed FPGA in the cloud architecture by Suhaib et al. [7].

Nastic et al.

In [8], Nastic et al. take advantage of the benefits of the serverless computing paradigm and its expansion to the edge, giving rise to the edge-cloud continuum. Serverless computing is presented as a model for the development of modern, cloud-native applications due to its low management overhead, easy deployment, scale-to-zero, and promise of optimized costs.

Serverless Computing Fabric (SCF) is defined as a software architecture where an application is decomposed into ‘triggers’ and ‘actions’ or functions. In general, the platforms allow these developer-defined functions to be hosted and executed, facilitating the development, management, scaling, and operation of these functions.

The Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) approach is used as the programming and execution model in serverless computing. Specifically, it is mentioned that areas such as Edge Intelligence (EI) and AI can benefit significantly from the principles and models of serverless computing at the edge, as these applications are known to be challenging to operate but benefit considerably from specialized infrastructure. Figure 2.8 shows the three main layers: the FaaS Runtime, which provides the necessary support to run and manage the SCF functions; the FaaS Platform Layer, which provides the core services that support the FaaS Runtime; and the FaaS Platform Layer, which is responsible for managing the edge-cloud infrastructure resources.

Figure 2.8: Serverless Computing Fabric Architecture [8]

2.3.2 Virtualization based on containers

Lamees et al.

The heterogeneous cloud infrastructure model proposed by Lamees et al. [9] is a microservices-based approach to FPGAs deployment and management in the cloud, which allows users to access and schedule FPGA resources remotely through a web interface. Figure 2.9 shows the microservice architecture where multiple Docker containers are used to manage interaction between components, automate the FPGA design flow, remotely program FPGA hardware, and monitor devices. The proposed system introduces a web microservice architecture and software implementation that enables remote programming of an FPGA board without the need for Hardware Development or Software Development Kits (HDK or SDK). It automates the entire FPGA design flow, from Hardware Description Language (HDL) design entry to test-bench verification, through a web-based interface. This user-friendly system requires only knowledge of HDL like Verilog and VHDL, or high-level programming languages like OpenCL, simplifying the FPGA programming process and making it accessible to a broader range of users.

Figure 2.9: Lamees et al. proposed microservice [9]

Ojika et al.

In [10], Ojika et al. suggest a resource provisioning architecture that utilizes Docker containers for PCIe-based FPGAs. The architecture comprises a pool of available kernel functions for acceleration. A worker container is deployed per kernel function on a worker node as shown in Figure 2.10. Each worker container implements a runtime that interacts with the FPGA hardware, scheduling its pre-designed kernel function when resources are available. A server node receives hardware acceleration requests through a web application. The server node transfers the request to the worker container that manages the kernel function via a web socket. The worker container schedules the kernel when feasible (i.e. when the required resources are available). Worker containers operate as privileged containers, meaning that the containers do not have any hardware access limitations, breaking the intended container isolation.

Figure 2.10: Ojika et al. proposed architecture [10]

Long et al.

Authors in [11] follow a similar approach to the previous paper to implement a Kubernetes-based architecture for FPGA resource virtualization and deployment. The system architecture comprises a cluster of nodes, each consisting of a host CPU and an FPGA. The Kubernetes scheduler deploys containerized applications on these nodes. However, this approach requires users to reconfigure and access the underlying hardware explicitly, which makes applications platform-dependent. In addition, similar to previous work, the containerized applications operate in privileged mode. The virtualized architecture of FPGA is shown in Figure 2.11.

Figure 2.11: Infrastructure using Docker to package FPGA [11]

2.4 Comparison

As seen in the state of the art, FPGA accelerators are being applied in various systems, from embedded systems to cloud computing, because of their high performance and energy efficiency. Given the scale of deployment, there is a need for efficient application development, resource management, and scalable systems, which makes FPGA virtualization extremely important. Therefore, it is increasingly common to use FPGA virtualization methods and hardware infrastructures to address multi-tenancy execution, multi-FPGA acceleration, flexibility, resource management, and security. This makes it difficult to differentiate between FPGA cloud hardware acceleration and virtualization infrastructures in most works discussed above.

To make comparisons of infrastructure characteristics, it has been decided to use some of the classification and objectives in terms of virtualization proposed by Vaishnav et al. in [26]. Table 2.1 The four characteristics outlined in Table 2.1 indicate the type of virtualization based on the division described in the section, whether they support multi-user functionality, the level of scalability, depending on whether they include one or more FPGAs and support multi-user capabilities, and whether they support edge-cloud continuum.

Infrastructure	Virtualization	Multi-tenancy	Scalability	Edge-Cloud Continuum
Leeser et al. [1]	-	✓	High	X
RC2F [2]	Node Level VMMs	✓	Medium	X
RACOS [3]	Node Level VMMs	X	Low	X
Lallet et al. [4]	Node Level Container	✓	Medium	X
Mandebi et al. [5]	Node Level VMMs	✓	Medium	X
Knodel et al. [6]	Node Level VMMs	✓	High	X
Suhaib et al. [7]	Node Level VMMs	✓	Medium	X
Nastic et al. [8]	Node Level VMMs & Containers	✓	High	✓
Lamees et al. [9]	Node Level Containers	X	Low	X
Ojika et al. [10]	Node Level Containers	✓	Medium	X
Long et al. [11]	Node Level Containers	✓	High	X
This work	Multi-node Containers	✓	High	✓

Table 2.1: Comparison of infrastructures.

Contrary to the existing works in the state of the art, this work proposes a solution compatible with the entire spectrum of reconfigurable computing resources, from the cloud to the edge. On top of that, none of the works covered in this chapter have an edge-oriented implementation, which is another novel contribution of this Master Thesis. The proposed architecture combines the user-agnostic orchestration of containerized applications provided by Kubernetes with the hardware abstraction provided by ARTICo³. This enables a single user application (i.e., hardware acceleration request) to be offloaded seamlessly to any computing resource across the continuum, regardless of the underlying hardware, and multi-tenancy thanks to the DPR capabilities.

3 Infrastructure for reconfigurable hardware acceleration in the cloud

This project is based on a distributed hardware acceleration infrastructure called ARTICo³, developed previously at CEI (Centro de Electronica Industrial). This infrastructure was implemented for embedded devices, so it has been adapted to the cloud to ensure compatibility with the edge-cloud continuum.

This chapter is divided into two main sections. The first section provides a comprehensive breakdown of the ARTICo³ architecture, detailing its various components and their functions. The second section discusses the necessary modifications made to adapt this architecture for PCIe-based platforms. Finally, it outlines the modifications implemented in the infrastructure to monitor consumption and performance.

3.1 Baseline Architecture: ARTICo³

ARTICo³ [12] is an open-source run-time reconfigurable processing framework for high-performance embedded computing. It offers adaptive computing performance, energy efficiency, and fault tolerance on demand.

The ARTICo³ framework, as shown in Figure 3.1, provides three components to deploy reconfigurable and adaptive multi-accelerator systems:

- A processing architecture enabled with DPR to leverage data- and task-level parallelism, featuring adaptive performance, fault tolerance, and energy efficiency.
- An automated toolchain for generating and implementing reconfigurable multi-accelerator systems from low-level HDL or high-level C/C++ and HLS.
- A library that handles memory management, FPGA reconfiguration, and multi-accelerator scheduling and execution transparently at runtime.

Figure 3.1: The ARTICo³ framework [12].

3.1.1 Architecture

The ARTICo³ architecture is a hardware-based processing architecture designed for adaptive high-performance embedded computing. The architecture, as shown in Figure 3.2 uses a slot-based partitioning of the reconfigurable fabric to leverage DPR following a multi-accelerator approach that offers software-like flexibility while maintaining hardware-like performance during execution.

Like many reconfigurable computing architectures, ARTICo³ divides the FPGA fabric into static and reconfigurable regions. The static region contains all the logical resources that remain constant throughout regular system operation. In contrast, the dynamic region is dedicated to application-specific logic, which can be modified entirely throughout the operational process. In ARTICo³, the dynamic region is divided into multiple subregions known as reconfigurable slots. The ARTICo³ allows the instantiation of a variable number of hardware accelerators that can be configured in reconfigurable slots, making the system scalable.

ARTICo³ accelerators execute using a GPU-like Single Instruction, Multiple Threads (SIMT) parallel computing model, utilizing multiple accelerator replicas to exploit performance scalability and power consumption tradeoffs at run time. In this regard, ARTICo³ can exploit two different levels of parallelism:

- **Task-level:** To achieve task-level parallelism, hardware accelerators with different application-specific functionalities and different input data can be executed concurrently.
- **Data-level:** To achieve data-level parallelism, hardware accelerators with the same application-specific functionality but different input data can run concurrently.

The ARTICo³ architecture distributes data to be processed by the hardware accelerators without user intervention, abstracting the underlying system hardware from the user's application. For this purpose, as shown in Figure 3.2, communication with the different hardware accelerators uses two communication channels, one based on memory-map registers for control signals and one memory-based for data movement through burst DMA transactions.

Figure 3.2: The ARTICo³ architecture block diagram [12].

The data shuffler is responsible for interfacing the hardware accelerators with the rest of the system, masking the double communication behind two Advanced eXtensible Interface 4 (AXI4)

communication interfaces. This allows efficient communication between an external memory and the hardware accelerators by accessing them as if they were a unified memory region and allowing data transmission in data bursts.

3.1.2 Toolchain

The ARTICo³ framework offers an automatic toolchain that lets users transparently generate reconfigurable systems from host application and hardware accelerator descriptions. Users only need to provide the host application in C/C++ code and the kernels in low-level HDL or C/C++ descriptions compatible with HLS tools. The ARTICo³ toolchain encapsulates user-defined hardware accelerators within an automatically generated wrapper connected to the Data Shuffler. This wrapper includes memory banks and configuration registers, which are used to control the hardware accelerators via the addressing scheme described in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: The ARTICo³ wrapper [12].

3.1.3 Runtime

The ARTICo³ framework provides a runtime library that presents an API for user applications to perform various operations, including system initialization and cleanup, DPR for loading the accelerators, managing memory buffers between the application and accelerators, and executing accelerators. The runtime is responsible for performing the low-level task requested by the user application via the API, such as hardware reconfiguration or DMA transfers, using the appropriate OS drivers depending on the specific computing system. Therefore, the user application is separated from the hardware. The user can control the generated hardware accelerators via the ARTICo³ runtime API from the application code, whose main functions are shown in Table 3.1.

Group	Function	Description
Platform	artico3_init	Initializes the runtime and loads the static system
	artico3_exit	Releases the runtime and cleans the environment
Slot	artico3_load	Loads a kernel in a slot and sets its configuration
	artico3_unload	Removes any previous slot configuration
Memory	artico3_alloc	Allocates a DMA-capable memory buffer for a kernel port
	artico3_free	Frees the memory buffer associated to a kernel port
Kernel	artico3_kernel_create	Registers a kernel in the runtime (gets an ID)
	artico3_kernel_release	Removes a kernel from the runtime (frees the ID)
	artico3_kernel_execute	Executes a kernel asynchronously (delegate thread)
	artico3_kernel_wait	Waits for kernel completion
	artico3_kernel_reset	Reset all accelerators of a given kernel
	artico3_kernel_wcfg	Writes data to kernel registers
	artico3_kernel_rcfg	Reads data from kernel registers
Monitor	artico3_hw_get_pmc_<name>	Access the specific PMC and gets its current value

Table 3.1: ARTICo³ Runtime API

3.2 Integrating ARTICo³ in PCIe-based platforms

The originally available version of the ARTICo³ toolchain was designed for Multiprocessor System-on-Chip (MPSoC) FPGAs (i.e., high-performance embedded systems supporting AMD Zynq and Zynq UltraScale+ devices). In these devices, the host processor is integrated on the same device as the reconfigurable logic, so ARTICo³ transparently communicates between them via memory-mapped registers (control bus) and via DMA burst transfers (data bus). However, PCIe-based platforms (such as AMD Xilinx Alveo cards) present the host processor and the programmable logic in two separate devices, communicated via a high-speed interface, specifically PCIe. ARTICo³ was, therefore, not directly compatible with this type of system, preventing the virtualization of the edge-cloud continuum required in this project. Thus, it was necessary to adapt this infrastructure so all the commands and data exchanges between the processor, and the programmable logic is carried out through PCIe instead of using on-chip buses.

3.2.1 Hardware Setup

The FPGA chosen for this project as a PCIe-based platform is shown in Figure 3.4. It is an Alveo U250 Data Center Accelerator from manufacturer AMD Xilinx.¹⁰ The FPGA is located inside an Ultra SuperServer SYS-620U-TNR from the manufacturer SUPERMICRO.¹¹ The communication between the host and the FPGA, as shown in Figure 3.5, is via a PCIe Gen3x16 interface, which allows a transfer rate of 8GT/s for each of the 16 lanes, reaching a bandwidth of 15.8GB/s (126Gbit/s).

Figure 3.4: Alveo U250 FPGA.

Figure 3.5: Block diagram of the ARTICo³ components integrated on a cloud-oriented device (AMD Alveo).

¹⁰<https://www.xilinx.com/products/boards-and-kits/alveo/u250.html#specifications>

¹¹<https://www.supermicro.com/en/products/system/datasheet/sys-620u-tnr>

3.2.2 Alveo U250 Data Center Accelerator Card

AMD Alveo™ U250 is a data acceleration card developed by Xilinx, designed to deliver high performance for data center applications and intensive computing environments. Based on FPGA technology, the Alveo U250 offers significant flexibility and parallel processing capability, allowing users to customize hardware acceleration for specific applications.

Alveo U250 main features:

- **FPGA Architecture:** Utilizes Xilinx’s UltraScale+ series FPGA, providing advanced processing capabilities and flexibility for a wide range of workloads.
- **High-Capacity Memory:** Equipped with up to 64 GB of DDR4 memory and HBM2 (High Bandwidth Memory), enabling fast and efficient access to large data sets.
- **High Bandwidth:** Offers high-speed interfaces, including PCIe Gen3 x16 and Gen4 x8, as well as network ports up to 100 GbE, facilitating rapid data transfer.
- **Support for AI and ML Applications:** Optimized for artificial intelligence and machine learning tasks, providing acceleration for both inference and training of models.

After studying the platform’s features, the ARTICo³ subsystems that needed to be adapted to the PCIe-based scheme were (i) the control of the acceleration requests offloaded onto the FPGA fabric, (ii) the data transfers between the processor and the FPGA, and (iii) the reconfiguration mechanism of the FPGA logic. These changes have been made through the implementation of the Xilinx Direct Memory Access (XDMA) bridge subsystem [13] and are explained in more detail below. In addition, Figure 3.5 shows a block diagram of a cloud structure with the integration of ARTICo³ once it has been adapted for this type of platform.

3.2.3 DMA/Bridge Subsystem for PCI Express

The XDMA subsystem for UltraScale+ is a high-performance DMA engine designed by Xilinx to facilitate efficient data transfer between host memory and the FPGA’s internal memory or peripherals in UltraScale+ devices. This subsystem is integral for applications that require high throughput and low latency data movement, such as high-performance computing. In addition to this hardware resource, AMD Xilinx provides IPs to facilitate communication between AXI-PCIe interfaces. One of the available Intellectual Property (IPs) is the “DMA/Bridge Subsystem for PCI Express” [13], as shown in the Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: DMA/Bridge Subsystem for PCI Express block diagram [13].

Main Features:

- **High Throughput:** The XDMA engine supports high-speed data transfer rates, leveraging the PCIe Gen3 or Gen4 interfaces to achieve efficient communication between the host system and the FPGA.
- **Flexible Data Movement:** It allows for flexible data transfers, including scatter-gather and direct memory access operations.
- **AXI Interface:** The XDMA subsystem uses the Advanced eXtensible Interface (AXI) standard for internal data movement within the FPGA, providing a standardized and efficient method for connecting different IP blocks and peripherals within the FPGA.
- **Host and Device Drivers:** Xilinx provides both host-side and device-side drivers to support the XDMA subsystem, ensuring seamless integration with different operating systems and simplifying the development process.

Once the capabilities offered by the IP are known, the following is a detailed explanation of how it has been used to adapt to the previously mentioned ARTICo³ subsystems.

Data-plane

The ARTICo³ architecture employs a standardized interconnection that accepts burst transfers exclusively designed for efficient data movement. In addition, a DMA engine is required to transfer data from the host processor to the accelerators efficiently. This controller is memory-mapped through an AXI4-Full interconnection, which is instantiated in the device to perform the data transfers to the ARTICo³ accelerators. It was necessary to adapt this architecture to enable DMA transfers from the host processor through the PCIe, instead of controlling them from an on-chip processor, as shown in Figure 3.5.

For this purpose, the XDMA IP was instantiated between the PCIe port and the AXI4-Full on-chip bus, as shown in Figure 3.5. This module performs translations between the host processor and the FPGA and gives the host processor access to the DMA engine to perform burst transfers. These direct memory transfers can be either Host-to-Card (H2C) or Card-to-Host (C2H), being scalable to 4 channels each.

Control-plane

The original ARTICo³ implementation uses a standard register-based AXI4-Lite interface, enabling the processor to perform configuration/control accesses to the accelerators. The required commands include triggering the start of the accelerators, configuring how DMA burst transfers are delivered to the accelerators, and accessing internal status registers of the accelerators (i.e., `#errors`, `#cycles`, `#slots`). It was necessary for the cloud platform to adapt the architecture to access the control resources through the PCIe.

For this purpose, the bridge module discussed above was also required between the PCIe and the AXI4-Lite bus. This module also gives the host processor access to the configuration, control, and status registers of the FPGA.

The ARTICo³ runtime library, based on a Linux OS, includes the necessary FPGA and DMA drivers, which perform memory management and multi-accelerator scheduling during kernel execution. However, this driver was explicitly designed for MPSoC FPGAs, so it has been necessary to use the Xilinx XDMA driver for cloud-based devices.¹² This driver allows the control of DMA burst transfers from the host processor in the server.

Partial Reconfiguration Controller

The original ARTICo³ implementation performs DPR via the Processor Configuration Access Port (PCAP) available on Zynq devices, which is a DMA-powered reconfiguration port that enables loading both static and partial bitstreams.

However, there is no PCAP on cloud platforms since no processor is embedded on the FPGA. Instead, a configuration port named Media Configuration Access Port (MCAP) is available explicitly for reconfiguration over PCIe for Ultrascale and UltraScale+ devices. When enabled, this port is integrated into the PCIe block, directly accessible from the host via the PCIe bridge module. As previously stated, the ARTICo³ runtime library uses a driver specifically designed for MPSoC FPGAs. Therefore, it has also been modified to use the appropriate driver to handle DPR via PCIe. The Xilinx XVSEC driver has been used for this purpose.¹²

¹²https://github.com/Xilinx/dma_ip_drivers

Start-up configuration

Cloud platforms used as PCIe endpoints must be prepared for system enumeration by the host within 100ms after boot.¹³ To meet this requirement, the boot configuration had to be modified.

The selected configuration mode, called Tandem, divides the bitstream into two stages. The first stage configures the PCIe through an Electrically Erasable Programmable Read-Only Memory (EEPROM) (see in Figure 3.5) and the second stage loads the rest of the static bitstream (i.e., the ARTICo³ static architecture) through the PCIe link.

3.2.4 DFX

Dynamic Function eXchange (DFX) [27] is the most up-to-date reconfiguration infrastructure/framework for Xilinx products, which allows DPR of the FPGA fabric during operation. This capability enables different portions of the FPGA to be reprogrammed with new functionality without interrupting the rest of the system, providing significant benefits in terms of flexibility, resource utilization, and performance. A reconfigurable design such as the one proposed, with a static and a dynamic region requires a DFX-compliant design.

In fact, the template utilized in the ARTICo³ toolchain generates an overlay in the FPGA with 16 reconfigurable slots. Figure 3.7 shows the floorplan of the implemented design, where all reconfigurable regions (highlighted in red) are loaded with an AES-256 CTR kernel (blue). Note that the ARTICo³ architecture (green) makes a connection the with each hardware accelerator using the ARTICo³ point-to-point interface (white). The static region of the design is formed by the shuffler (green) and the “DMA/Bridge subsystem for PCIe” (orange).

¹³<https://docs.amd.com/r/en-US/pg213-pcie4-ultrascale-plus/Tandem-Configuration>

Figure 3.7: ARTICo³ floorplan in Alveo U250.

DFX Decouplers

Performing DPR involves a problem when there are communication signals and buses between the static and reconfigurable regions. While performing such reconfiguration these signals and buses may be in unexpected states that cause the bus to block. In this case, the shuffler is a reconfigurable block that uses AXI4-Lite interfaces for control, AXI4-Full for data transmission, and an interrupt signal. Therefore, AMD Xilinx offers IPs called DFX Decoupler [28] and DFX AXI Shutdown Manager [29] to isolate these critical parts of the system during the reconfiguration period. When active, these decouplers introduce user-configurable values that guarantee the integrity of the system.

Figure 3.8: Block diagram of the DFX Decouplers.

3.2.5 XDMA driver

AMD Xilinx offers the possibility of installing a driver in the operating system at the host that allows communication between the host via PCIe and the DMA/Bridge module of the endpoint. On the one hand, it offers an abstraction layer in the configuration of the DMA interface channels of the endpoint that allows the H2C and C2H operations to be carried out in a simple way. In turn, it provides easy access to the memory-mapped registers in the host of the AXI-Lite and AXI-MM bypass interfaces of the endpoint. This access is provided by the character type drivers generated by the driver when detecting the XDMA devices on the endpoint.

Interrupts in Linux coming through PCI Express are managed more easily by the operating system thanks to the use of the driver. In this project, we have analyzed how the interrupts that reach the IP internally are translated into event descriptors in Linux through the driver. However, they have not been implemented in the final architecture.

3.2.6 Implemented architecture

Figure 3.9 shows the final system implemented in the Alveo U250 platform, in which the different elements described in the previous sections can be seen. A view of the design implemented is shown in the ??.

Figure 3.9: Block diagram of the ARTICo³ components integrated on Alveo U250.

3.3 Power and Performance Monitor

The Xilinx Alveo U250 FPGA is designed to accelerate various data center applications by providing high performance and energy efficiency. Monitoring power and performance metrics is crucial for optimizing resource utilization, managing energy consumption, and ensuring reliable operation. To achieve these objectives, the AMD Xilinx offers the AMD Alveo Card Management Solution Subsystem (CMS) [30], based on a Microblaze soft-core. CMS firmware autonomously reads sensor information from the satellite controller device (external micro-controller unit) over UART, as shown in Figure 3.10 and writes instantaneous, maximum, and average values to a shared memory for collection by the host software. Sensor information is monitored and gathered for voltages, currents, temperatures, fan speed, and power.

For real-time performance monitoring, custom scripts have been used to measure both kernel execution time and the sending and receiving of data. This data is stored for further processing and visualization.

Figure 3.10: CMS Subsystem diagram.

4 Edge-Cloud Virtualization of FPGAs

The integration of FPGAs is becoming increasingly prevalent in the modern computing landscape, offering outstanding flexibility and performance acceleration. This integration spans across diverse environments, from the cloud to the edge, forming what is known as the edge-cloud continuum. Virtualizing the FPGA infrastructure within this continuum is essential to creating a dynamic, adaptable, and scalable computing environment that meets the evolving demands of today's applications.

Virtualization of the FPGA infrastructure entails abstracting physical hardware resources into virtual instances, enabling multiple users and applications to efficiently share and utilize FPGA resources. This abstraction layer not only enhances resource management but also fosters flexibility and agility in deploying FPGA-accelerated solutions across distributed environments.

In the context of the edge-cloud continuum, FPGA virtualization offers compelling advantages. It seamlessly integrates FPGA resources into existing architectures, facilitating efficient utilization across diverse deployment scenarios. Dynamic resource allocation based on workload demands ensures optimal resource utilization and performance efficiency. Additionally, FPGA virtualization enhances security by providing isolation between different FPGA applications or users.

With this premise, a series of design requirements have been established that the proposed architecture must meet in order to optimally address the proposed objective. The designed edge-cloud continuum architecture based on FPGAs will be explained throughout this chapter in order to show how the following design requirements have been addressed and solved:

- Hardware acceleration implementation in every node.
- Compatibility of user applications between nodes.
- Seamless deployment of user applications across the continuum.

4.1 Proposed Infrastructure

This project proposes the development of an infrastructure to support the edge-cloud continuum, enabling the seamless deployment of user applications across the whole infrastructure. For this reason, it was first necessary to ensure the compatibility of the different applications between the various nodes and underlying device technologies. As a differential requirement, the proposed infrastructure will support the deployment of reconfigurable hardware accelerators on each node, using ARTiCo³ as the underlying reconfiguration technology.

Figure 4.1: Proposed edge-cloud continuum infrastructure.

Figure 4.1 shows the edge-cloud continuum infrastructure proposed. Next, it is explained how this infrastructure combines ARTICo³ with Kubernetes to provide the expected features.

4.2 Hardware acceleration implementation in every node

Although it could be possible to include pure CPU-based nodes in the infrastructure, this work is focused on extending the usage of FPGAs and MPSoC FPGA devices in the edge-cloud continuum. For this reason, it will be assumed that all the nodes in the proposed infrastructure include an FPGA fabric in which the extended ARTICo³ architecture (the cloud, fog, or edge version, depending on the platform) has been implemented. Therefore, each node in the continuum can support reconfigurable hardware accelerators, transfer data to and from them, and execute them. Furthermore, ARTICo³'s DPR capabilities enable data- and task-level parallelism, with multiple replicas of one or more accelerators on each node. Note that nodes closer to the edge have fewer resources, which limits the number of hardware accelerators per system.

4.3 Compatibility of hardware-accelerated user applications between nodes via containerization

The proposed infrastructure is based on containerized applications to ensure compatibility of user applications between the nodes of the continuum. Compatibility is achieved because containers embed any necessary dependencies or components. In addition, to access the underlying hardware from the user application, the ARTICo³ runtime is also embedded in the container. Therefore, the user application can command the ARTICo³ runtime to perform low-level hardware tasks (e.g., DPR hardware accelerator load or DMA-based data transfers) without any further dependency for the user.

This strategy allows the production of a multi-architecture container image during the creation of the containerized application. This image includes references to all the required host

applications and ARTICo³ runtime pairs to run the application on any node in the continuum. Therefore, when the containerized application is deployed on any node, a container that includes the host application compiled for that specific processor architecture and the ARTICo³ runtime specific to that platform (i.e., cloud, fog, or edge) is executed. Consequently, the containerized application can be executed on any node in the continuum, and the low-level hardware operations required for the underlying ARTICo³ architecture will be performed transparently by the specific ARTICo³ runtime for that particular platform. Therefore, the containerization strategy combined with the virtualization capabilities of ARTICo³ allows the transparent compatibility of user applications between nodes.

4.4 Seamless deployment of user applications across the continuum

The proposed infrastructure integrates each computing device as a node within a computing continuum. Kubernetes manages the entire continuum through a master node (as part of an existing node or a dedicated one, as the continuum administrator decides). The master is responsible for identifying and monitoring new nodes and managing container deployment among the nodes. The rest of the nodes function as Kubernetes agents. Each agent has a local container runtime and serves requests from the master, such as deploying containers, generating local storage, and managing the network. They manage and monitor themselves and report back to the master. This is done transparently for the user. For instance, when a user commands the deployment of a certain number of replicas of an application, the master node decides which continuum nodes are suitable for the deployment and how many instances should execute each of the petitions. The process begins by requesting each selected agent to deploy the containerized image of the application with the decided number of instances. The agents then deploy the requested containers using the local container runtime and monitor their execution. The master and the agents maintain communication so that the appropriate containers can be restored in the event of a failure. Moreover, the application deployment can be rescaled during execution if needed, and even the entire infrastructure can be scaled by adding or modifying nodes as needed.

The implementation proposed in this project is based on K3S,¹⁴ an official lightweight Kubernetes distribution optimized for ARM processors. It has a minimal footprint since it includes only essential components, which makes it suitable for lower-end edge devices that may struggle with the resource demands of the standard Kubernetes distribution. However, the proposal is compatible with any other Kubernetes distribution.

¹⁴<https://k3s.io>

5 Validation

This section is divided into three parts. The first describes the experimental setup used for the infrastructure validation. The second evaluates ARTICo³ on standalone (i.e., isolated) platforms, each one corresponding to a specific edge-cloud continuum layer. The last one evaluates the proposed integrated edge-cloud continuum infrastructure. The results obtained are presented and discussed in each part of the evaluation.

5.1 Experimental Setup

An actual implementation has been created to evaluate the proposed edge-cloud continuum infrastructure. The structure mirrors that of Figure 4.1, but as a proof of concept, only one node per layer (cloud, fog, and edge) has been included. Thanks to the integration of Kubernetes, the infrastructure can be easily scaled by adding more nodes per layer, as has been previously described in Subsection 4.4. Table 5.1 describe the specific configuration of each of the FPGA-based systems used for the implementation of the infrastructure. Note that the host CPU used in the PCIe platform is the Intel Xeon Gold 6338 with 128 cores.

Table 5.1: Edge-cloud continuum experimental setup.

Layer	Board (FPGA device)	Frequency		# Reconf. Slots (LUTs per Slot)
		CPU	FPGA	
Cloud	Alveo U250 (A-U250-P64G-PQ-G)	2 GHz	100 MHz	16 (44.1K)
Fog	Zynq UltraScale+ ZCU102 (XCZU9EG-2FFVB1156)	1.2 GHz	100 MHz	8 (21.6K)
Edge	PYNQ-Z1 (XC7Z020-1CLG400C)	650 MHz	100 MHz	4 (6.4K)

Since each board has a different amount of logic reconfigurable resources, the reconfigurable slots allocated in each platform vary in size (i.e., number of LUTs) and number, as shown in the rightmost column of Table 5.1. Note that the number of reconfigurable slots has been selected in consecutive powers of two for ease of comparison, despite the fact that the differences in available resources on the boards are greater, as will be discussed in the following sections.

5.2 ARTICo³ on isolated Edge-Cloud Continuum nodes

The inherent flexibility of FPGAs allows them to be reconfigured to suit different workloads, offering a customizable and efficient solution for computational tasks. This adaptability is crucial in cloud environments where resource availability can fluctuate. By leveraging elastic applications, which dynamically adjust their resource usage based on demand, users can maximize the utilization of FPGA resources, scaling up during peak demand to enhance performance and scaling down during off-peak times to save costs. This approach optimizes computational efficiency and reduces operational expenses, making it suitable for applications requiring high computational throughput or specialized processing capabilities.

This section has two objectives: first, to illustrate how the architecture can be actively adapted to the platform where it is deployed to explore the solution space for a given elastic application, and second, to compare the proposed solution with a software-based alternative. For this purpose, two different algorithms have been implemented in the ARTICo³ architecture: on the one hand, a block cipher algorithm (AES-256), described at HDL level, and, on the other hand, a 32-bit matrix multiplier using HLS.

5.2.1 Scenario 1: Matrix Multiplication

The scenario used to evaluate high-performance embedded computing is a matrix multiplication application described in HLS-compatible C code. This is a computationally intensive task widely used as a benchmark for evaluating parallel computing architectures and used in [12] to validate the architecture. A block-based nested multiplication procedure with 2 identical block layers has been implemented to exploit parallelism at both the algorithm and accelerator levels. This approach is used to enable mixed data-parallel and pipelined execution within each kernel instance and to support data-level parallelism with multiple accelerators.

The ARTICo³ kernel for matrix multiplication takes 64×64 32-bit values as input and multiplies them using the block-based algorithm mentioned above with a block size of 8×8 32-bit values, easily scaled to a 64×64 32-bit value block. The kernels have been generated with optimization directives for loop unrolling, array partitioning and pipelining to maximize the performance/area ratio.

In turn, block-based matrix multiplication has been implemented in software to validate the ARTICo³ implementation on cloud platforms. For both the software application and inside the hardware accelerators the block-based matrix multiplication algorithm layer shown in the Figure 5.1 has been used.

Figure 5.1: Block-based matrix multiplication.

Table 5.3 shows the resource utilization report of the matmul kernel when implemented on the PYNQ-Z1 and ZCU102 platforms. In this configuration, the ARTICo³ architecture has been designed with 4 reconfigurable slots for the PYNQ-Z1 and 8 for the ZCU102. As can be seen, in Table 5.2, since more resources are available per slot in the ZCU102, it is possible to scale the core to a block size of 16x16 32 bits instead of the 8x8 32 bits of the PYNQ-Z1.

	PYNQ-Z1 (Edge)		ZCU102 (Fog)	
	ARTICo ³	Matrix Multiplier	ARTICo ³	Matrix Multiplier
Info	4 slots VHDL (Vivado)	48 KiB memory, 3 banks 0 registers C + HLS (Vivado) 8x8 block size	8 slots VHDL (Vivado)	48 KiB memory, 3 banks 0 registers C + HLS (Vivado) 16x16 block size
LUTs	3780	1730	5107	2077
FFs	2366	1234	3763	425
DSPs	-	24	2	48
BRAMs	-	12	-	12

Table 5.2: Resource utilization of matrix multiplication kernel in PYNQ-Z1 and ZCU102 FPGAs

Table 5.3, on the other hand, shows the resource utilization report of two different configurations of the matmul kernel when implemented on an Alveo U250. Both configurations differ in the block size within each kernel instance: the basic configuration uses an 8x8 32-bit block size, while the parallel configuration uses 64x64 32-bit. In this scenario, the ARTICo³ architecture has 16 reconfigurable slots that can be filled with up to 16 kernel instances.

Alveo U250 (Cloud)			
	ARTICo ³	Matrix Multiplier	
Info	16 slots VHDL (Vivado)	48 KiB memory, 3 banks 0 registers C + HLS (Vivado) 8x8 block size (basic)	48 KiB memory, 3 banks 0 registers C + HLS (Vivado) 64x64 block size
LUTs	9404	1461	6770
FFs	6648	140	325
DSPs	2	24	192
BRAMs	-	12	12

Table 5.3: Resource utilization of Matrix Multiplication kernel in Alveo U250 FPGA

Figure 5.2 shows the performance results in this scenario with different matrix sizes deployed on the platforms with the configuration explained above. As seen, through this scalable scenario, you can deploy the same application with more parallelization on platforms with larger slots, i.e., with more resources. It should be noted that the increase in matrix size do not affect the ratio of execution times between the different platforms.

Figure 5.2: Matrix multiplication application execution time per platform, normalized to the cloud.

5.2.2 Scenario 2: AES Block Cipher

In the second validation scenario, the design space has been explored by scaling the Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language (VHDL) kernel to observe its impact on performance and the area it occupies within the slot. In this scenario, a block cipher (AES-256 in CTR mode, which allows parallelization during encryption) has been implemented, as block cipher is a computationally bounded kernel that enables better scalability potential. It should be noted that all accelerators described in this subsection have been done using a legacy stream from [14].

Table 5.5 shows the resource utilization report of the AES-256 CTR kernel when implemented on PYNQ-Z1 (edge) and ZCU102 (fog) platforms. In this configuration, the ARTICo³ architecture has 4 reconfigurable slots for the PYNQ-Z1 and 8 reconfigurable slots for the ZCU102 which can be filled with the same number of AES-256 CTR kernel instances as slots. As can be seen, the configurations differ in the number of parallel data paths available within each kernel instance, with one hardware thread being the basic configuration per accelerator and 2 hardware threads being the parallel configuration.

	PYNQ-Z1 (Edge)		ZCU102 (Fog)	
	ARTICo ³	AES-256 CTR	ARTICo ³	AES-256 CTR
Info	4 slots VHDL (Vivado)	64 KiB memory, 2 banks 13 registers VHDL (Vivado) 1 thread	8 slots VHDL (Vivado)	64 KiB memory, 2 banks 13 registers VHDL (Vivado) 2 threads
LUTs	3887	3597	5125	6990
FFs	2366	3715	3763	6574
DSPs	-	-	2	-
BRAMs	-	17	-	18

Table 5.4: Resource utilization of AES-256 CTR Encryption kernel in PYNQ-Z1 and ZCU102 FPGAs

On the other hand, Table 5.5 shows the resource utilization report of two different configurations of the AES-256 CTR when implemented on an Alveo U250. As can be seen, the configurations differ in the number of parallel data paths available within each kernel instance, with 4 hardware threads being the basic configuration per accelerator and 8 hardware threads being the parallel configuration. The ARTICo³ architecture in this scenario has 16 reconfigurable slots that can be filled with up to 16 kernel instances.

	Alveo U250 (Cloud)		
	ARTICo ³	AES-256 CTR	
Info	16 slots VHDL (Vivado)	64 KiB memory, 2 banks 13 registers VHDL (Vivado) 4 threads (basic)	64 KiB memory, 2 banks 13 registers VHDL (Vivado) 8 threads
LUTs	9405	14215	26584
FFs	6648	12282	23667
DSPs	2	-	-
BRAMs	-	20	24

Table 5.5: Resource utilization of AES-256 CTR Encryption kernel in Alveo U250 FPGA

In order to implement two or more parallel datapaths inside an AES-256 CTR hardware accelerator, the local memory partitioning has been modified according to the scheme shown in Figure 5.3. As can be seen, some address bits have been reordered before driving port A, although this does not alter the local memory map in each hardware accelerator from a static system (i.e., shuffler) point of view. However, to support additional input and output data streams for the second thread, the number of memory banks within the kernel instance has

been doubled. In addition, the CTR kernel configuration has also been adapted to fully support parallel encryption.

Figure 5.3: Memory bank partitioning of single versus multithreaded AES-256 CTR accelerators. [14]

Figure 5.4 shows the solution space of the AES-256 CTR kernel on the different platforms. Each platform has a different configuration (i.e., one, two, four, or eight parallel threads within each accelerator) depending on the slot size, and this results in reduced execution times when going from the edge to the cloud. It is worth noting that experimentation has shown that the internal execution time of the accelerator is much less than the time of sending and receiving data. Therefore, despite doubling the number of threads between the two configurations in the cloud platform, the total execution time is similar. This rises the need to optimize the data transfers in the future for further acceleration gains.

Figure 5.4: AES-256 CTR application execution time per platform, normalized to the cloud.

5.3 Edge-Cloud Continuum infrastructure

For a fair evaluation of the integrated setup provided in this project, user applications must be offloaded across the continuum. In addition, these applications must contain a wide range of unique execution profiles to be comparable to a real-world workload. To this end, a well-known benchmark suite for HLS-oriented accelerator evaluation called MachSuite [31] has been used. MachSuite provides 12 kernels (e.g., AES, FFT), some of them in multiple flavors, for a total of 19 different algorithms. These kernels are organized according to 12 relevant computation/communication patterns called *Dwarfs* [32]. It is important to note that 9 of the algorithms have been discarded due to logic resource limitations on the FPGA fabric of the edge and fog platforms. However, 8 of the 12 dwarfs are still present in the experiments, providing a reasonable diversity of kernels. Moreover, the matrix multiplication example in the ARTICo³ documentation and an HDL-based AES-256 CTR kernel, both used in the assessment of each individual platform from the previous section, have also been included in the user applications used for the experiments.¹⁵

Note that all the MachSuite benchmarks have been implemented without any performance optimizations, as they are used for infrastructure validation purposes rather than pursuing acceleration. On the other hand, matrix multiplication and AES-256 CTR applications have been optimized as mentioned in the previous section for the PCIe platform.

5.3.1 Assessment of Results

To evaluate the proposed infrastructure, the user applications mentioned above have been executed on each available platform, with as many accelerators in parallel as available reconfigurable slots (see Table 5.1). The applications have been containerized with Docker, resulting in a multi-architecture image for all three platforms. The set of applications have been accelerated in hardware throughout the edge-cloud continuum using the proposed infrastructure, with Kubernetes handling deployment and ARTICo³ managing the deployment of the reconfigurable accelerators. This section discusses the obtained results.

¹⁵<https://des-cei.github.io/tools/artico3/tutorials/matmul>

Figure 5.5: Execution time of each user application per platform, normalized to the cloud.

Figure 5.5 presents the execution time of each application when it is deployed on each platform, normalized to the fastest execution (i.e., the cloud, for which the normalized value is always one in the figure). The progression of the normalized execution time when moving from one platform to the others is similar for all the *MachSuite benchmarks*. This is because the hardware implementation of each application is identical on each platform, resulting in similar execution times between platforms. The difference in the number of parallel accelerators between platforms (16 slots for cloud, 8 for fog, and 4 for the edge, as shown in Table 5.1) is the reason for the provided acceleration. However, there are some variations between kernels. The execution time of an application depends also on both the software that manages the accelerators and the data transfer. The software benefits from a more powerful processor in the cloud, while the data transfer is slower due to communication overhead between different hosts and FPGA devices. Therefore, slight variations in execution times occur due to the nature of the application.

Nevertheless, in the case of the matrix multiplication application, the execution on the cloud showed a more significant difference than the execution on the other two devices due to the performance optimizations applied to the cloud platform. This indicates the potential benefits of utilizing both the acceleration provided by the number of parallel accelerators and the performance optimizations.

Table 5.6: Resource available per platform.

Platform	LUTs	FFs	DSPs	BRAMs	Maximum # of Reconfigurable Slots
Cloud	1,707,232	3,456,000	12,288	2,688	≈ 256 (32x)
Fog	274,080	548,160	2,520	912	≈ 42 (5.25x)
Edge	53,200	106,400	220	140	≈ 8 (1x)

These two aspects are related to the availability of resources in the system. Table 5.6 displays the resources of each device in the infrastructure used for these experiments, including the maximum number of reconfigurable slots that could be potentially used on each device based on the available resources, assuming a common slot size limited by that of the edge platform (see Table 5.1). This decision was taken to make the portability of hardware accelerators easier

among devices. Other alternatives, such as providing larger slots on larger devices, could be also explored.

The fog could theoretically accommodate over five times more accelerators in parallel than the edge. This difference could be even more noticeable when transitioning to the cloud, as it could allow up to 32 times more accelerators to be configured in parallel than the edge. Therefore, more resources could be available when moving closer to the cloud. This potentially enables an increase in parallel hardware accelerators, taking advantage of data parallelism to speed up execution. Furthermore, extra resources could allow more users to share in the multi-tenant scenario. This approach maximizes resource utilization and distributes the fixed cost of resources among users.

Table 5.7: Power consumption and reconfiguration time per platform.

Platform	Power Consumption	Reconfiguration Time per MB of bitstream
Cloud	23 W (6.57x)	265.387 ms (74.40x)
Fog	23 W (6.57x)	3.567 ms (1x)
Edge	3.5 W (1x)	19.242 ms (5.39x)

There are also some drawbacks to moving computation to the cloud. Table 5.7 displays the power consumption of each platform. The power consumption of the fog and edge platforms has been directly measured from their power supply, while for the cloud platform, the CMS subsystem [30] has been used to read platform-wide power consumption values from internal sensors. The table shows that shifting processing to the cloud results in higher power consumption (note that while the power consumption of the cloud and fog platforms is similar in our experimental setup, the power consumption of the cloud is expected to increase when all logic resources are utilized). This is true considering only power consumption due to the higher energy efficiency shown by devices optimized for the edge, even without considering the cost of moving data from the edge to the cloud, which has not been included in this work. Therefore, choosing which device to accelerate each application will require balancing the desired acceleration with the available power budget. In addition, it is essential to consider the reconfiguration time needed for each platform, as shown in Table 5.7. When comparing reconfiguration times, cloud platforms are slower than others due to the bitstream transfer between host and FPGA. Therefore, the bitstreams generated for the cloud platform are compressed to improve reconfigurations through PCIe. In contrast, systems integrating the processor and FPGA in the same device have more efficient mechanisms for hardware reconfiguration. For example, the board used for the fog in these experiments has a hard-core processor dedicated exclusively to reconfiguration [33], resulting in the shortest reconfiguration time. Therefore, it is more efficient in the cloud to accelerate tasks that run for long periods, reducing the impact of reconfiguration time compared to execution time. This approach is beneficial due to the acceleration provided by massively parallel execution and the performance optimizations that can be applied thanks to abundant resources.

Table 5.8: Kubernetes execution overhead per platform.

Platform	Overhead	
	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cloud	0.90%	0.20%
Fog	0.41%	0.56%
Edge	1.23%	1.67%

Finally, Table 5.8 shows the induced overhead when using our proposed infrastructure to run containerized applications via Kubernetes compared to the traditional non-containerized application execution. The data indicates that the overhead is slightly over 1% for the worst case, insignificant compared to the advantages of virtualization and portability provided by implementing Kubernetes in the proposed infrastructure.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

This project addresses the virtualization of reconfigurable systems for their integration in the edge-cloud continuum. In this regard, the ARTICo³ framework has been extended to support cloud platforms consisting of a host and an FPGA connected via PCIe. As a result, a user application can now be hardware-accelerated for edge, fog, and cloud without requiring knowledge of the underlying hardware. Additionally, ARTICo³ has been integrated with Kubernetes to create a microservices-based infrastructure. This enables users to seamlessly deploy and accelerate applications on any system within the edge-cloud continuum.

The results indicated that the overhead induced by the proposed infrastructure is barely over 1% in the worst case compared to traditional execution without containerization. This percentage is negligible, especially considering the benefits of proposed virtualization, including portability and scalability.

Additionally, the advantages and disadvantages of running applications in each of the layers of the continuum, in terms of resources, power consumption, and reconfiguration time, have been analyzed. It has been demonstrated that moving the compute to layers closer to the cloud allows us to apply performance optimizations (elastic applications) and increase the parallelism at the application level (accelerator replication), thus achieving higher acceleration levels and maximizing resource utilization. Despite the good results on the platform based on PCIe, a limitation has been observed concerning the other platforms in terms of data transfer time DMA over PCIe and reconfiguration time. In [34], after studying leading cloud providers such as Amazon, AWS, Alibaba, and Huawei, they concluded that hardware drivers strongly limit the performance of intercommunication in FPGA clouds, and a slight optimization of the DMA drivers for PCIe can generate a significant performance gain. To optimize DMA transfers over PCIe, it is proposed that in the future, a custom driver be made and the reconfiguration flow modified to explore other options.¹⁶

Various factors, including the nature of the task and specific characteristics, would influence the decision of which system to use for accelerating an application. In the future, we propose developing an intelligent resource management algorithm that will support scheduling decisions at the workload level based on the application's requirements, the available systems and resources, and the run-time behaviour of the system (which can in turn be obtained using data-driven models [35]). In addition, multi-tenant computing is a promising idea under the edge-cloud continuum, particularly at the cloud level, due to the abundance of resources. This approach maximizes the use of resources and, therefore, maximizes the return on investment in technology while spreading the static cost of the infrastructure among a more significant number of users. The ARTICo³ framework will be extended as future work to support multi-tenant execution on the same device simultaneously.

¹⁶<https://docs.amd.com/r/en-US/xapp1338-fast-partial-reconfiguration-pci-express>

7 Time planning and budgeting

This section shows the planning that was carried out for this project through the Gantt chart in Figure 7.1, followed by the budget in Table 7.1, where all costs are shown.

Figure 7.1: Execution time of each user application per platform, normalized to the cloud.

Material	Price/unit(€)	Quantity	Total price
A-U250-P64G-PQ-G	9.000 €	1	9.000 €
Ultra SuperServer 620U-TNR	15.000 €	1	15.000 €
Vivado licence	2.800 €	1	2.800 €
Engineering hours	30,00 €	450	13.500,00 €
TOTAL	-	-	40.300,00 €

Table 7.1: Project budget

8 Social and professional responsibility

In the rapidly evolving landscape of cloud and edge computing, the integration and virtualization of PCIe-based reconfigurable multi-accelerator systems represent a significant technological advancement. This project, aimed at enhancing computational efficiency and flexibility, also brings with it a set of social and professional responsibilities that must be carefully considered.

The convergence of advanced technologies in a seamless edge-cloud continuum has the potential to impact various aspects of society, from economic growth to digital inclusion and environmental sustainability. As engineers and researchers, we bear the responsibility to ensure that our innovations are developed and deployed ethically, sustainably, and inclusively.

This project can significantly contribute to several United Nations SDGs shown in Figure 8.1. Below is an analysis of the impact on relevant SDGs:

Figure 8.1: Sustainable Development Goals.

- **SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy**

Impact: Virtualized accelerator systems can optimize energy usage in data centers by enabling more efficient resource allocation and utilization. These systems reduce unnecessary energy consumption by tailoring computational power to the needs of specific tasks dynamically.

Contribution: The project supports improving energy efficiency by leveraging the reconfigurability of hardware to balance loads and reduce energy waste, ultimately contributing to more sustainable energy use in cloud computing infrastructures.

- **SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth**

Impact: Introducing advanced virtualization techniques for hardware accelerators can stimulate innovation and create high-tech job opportunities in cloud computing, hardware design, and software development.

Contribution: By enhancing the efficiency and capability of cloud services, the project promotes sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth. Additionally, it can create new industries and job markets focused on cutting-edge technology development.

- **SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure**

Impact: This project promotes inclusive and sustainable industrialization by building resilient infrastructure and fostering innovation.

Contribution: By advancing the virtualization of FPGA resources in the cloud, the project supports the development of a robust and flexible infrastructure capable of adapting to diverse and evolving computational demands. This enhances the capacity for innovation across various industries reliant on high-performance computing.

- **SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities**

Impact: Improved computational efficiency and reduced energy consumption in data centers can support the development of smart city technologies that rely on cloud-based services.

Contribution: By providing more efficient processing power for smart city applications, such as real-time data analysis for traffic management and environmental monitoring, the project contributes to making cities more sustainable and resilient.

- **SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production**

Impact: Virtualizing and optimizing the use of FPGA resources ensures that computational power is used more responsibly, reducing the environmental footprint of data centers.

Contribution: This project supports sustainable consumption and production patterns by maximizing the utility of existing hardware resources and minimizing waste through efficient virtualization and dynamic resource allocation.

- **SDG 13: Climate Action**

Impact: The energy efficiencies gained from this project can contribute to reducing the carbon footprint of data centers, which are significant electricity consumers.

Contribution: By optimizing resource usage and reducing energy consumption, the project aids in mitigating the impact of climate change through more sustainable and environmentally friendly computing practices.

- **SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals**

Impact: This project necessitates collaboration between hardware manufacturers, software developers, and cloud service providers, fostering partnerships that can drive further technological and sustainable development.

Contribution: By encouraging multi-stakeholder partnerships, the project promotes the sharing of knowledge, expertise, and technology, contributing to the achievement of sustainable development goals through collaborative innovation.

Conclusion

The virtualization of PCIe-based reconfigurable multi-accelerator systems for the edge-cloud continuum has a multifaceted impact on various SDGs. It promotes energy efficiency, economic growth, resilient infrastructure, sustainable urban development, responsible resource consumption, climate action, and collaborative partnerships. By integrating these advanced technologies into cloud computing infrastructures, the project enhances technological capabilities and drives progress toward a more sustainable and equitable future.

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